

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ROGERS****FIRST NAME: LESLIE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: WPS Office

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is **not** a category of difference between standard American English and standard British English?
 Same spelling, same pronunciation.¹
 Different pronunciation, same spelling.
 Different spelling, same pronunciation.
 Same words, different or additional meanings.
2. Why do researchers use secondary sources in research and essay writing?
 To acknowledge and respond to the perspectives of other researchers.²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 25-26.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36-37.

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: .

- To criticize the points of view of other researchers.
 - To replicate the researcher's work.
 - Because secondary sources are more reliable than primary research.
3. When should materials from other sources be cited?
- When quoting exact words from a source.**³
 - When using your original ideas.
 - When citing common knowledge.
 - When citing your own personal experiences.
4. Which of the following is **not** a source of potential bias in dissertation research?
- Experience bias.
 - Population bias.
 - Policy bias.
 - Reading bias.**⁴
5. Select the type of measure that is typically used in quantitative research.
- Focus groups.
 - Documents.
 - Unobtrusive observations.**⁵
 - Questions using mainly open-ended items.

³ Ibid., 140.

⁴ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 8-9.

⁵ Ibid., 37.

Deleted: .

Deleted: Florida: Creative Commons

Formatted: Justified

6. Which list shows the correct order of dissertation organization?
- Table of Contents, Acknowledgements, List of Tables, List of Figures.
 - Acknowledgements, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures.**⁶
 - Table of Contents, Acknowledgements, List of Figures, List of Tables.
 - Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Figures, List of Tables.
7. Which of the following items should **not** be included in the introduction chapter?
- Recommendations.**⁷
 - Rationale and Significance.
 - Research Questions.
 - Problem Statement.
8. Which research paradigm is referred to as advocacy and focuses on social justice?
- Pragmatism.
 - Social constructivism.
 - Critical Theory.**⁸
 - Postpositivism.
9. Which of the following methods is a systematic inquiry that aims to find effective solutions to complex problems faced in communities?
- Phenomenology.

⁶ Ibid., 66.

⁷ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 74.

⁸ Ibid., 150.

Deleted: From

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: London

Deleted: age

- Case study.
- Grounded Theory.
- Action Research.**⁹

10. What section of the dissertation outlines the design and manner in which the study was conducted?

- Literature Review.
- Abstract.
- Findings.
- Methodology.**¹⁰

⁹ Ibid., 179.

¹⁰ Ibid., 435.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

Deleted: ,

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: From

Deleted: ondon:

Deleted: Sage

Deleted: ,

Deleted: Florida: Creative Commons